

Documentating Data

Tip 1: Select Tools that Help Manage Data and Metadata

Consider an
Electronic Lab
Notebook

Follow
Established
Metadata
Standards

Supplement
Datasets with
Explanatory
Documentation

Tip 2: README Files are for more than Programming

What is a README File?

What: A README file is the first thing users of your data, software, or hardware will read. It is a text file that contains important information about your output and explains how users can navigate your other files. You can think of it as a roadmap you leave for others, or even a future version of yourself!

Why: If data cannot be understood, it cannot be reused! README files solve this problem by providing critical information about data creation and organization. README files help other, but they can help you remember important details too!

How: The RDM Team can help you draft your README files. We also recommend using the [Cornell University README Template!](#)

What to Include in a README

1. Basic information about the project and contact information for the project leads.
2. Description of the resource, its file structure, and any information needed to interpret the materials, such as variable name explanations.
3. Briefly describe the methods that were used to generate the data. You can also include links to relevant outside resources.
4. What licenses you have assigned to your outputs. Be clear and use common license options whenever possible.
5. Links to other outputs that are related to the resource you are sharing. These can be links to other datasets or DOIs for related publications.

RDM Homepage

How to Reach the RDM Team

Anyone at univie can reach-out to the RDM team for help. You can reach us at rdm@univie.ac.at or find our webpage at rdm.univie.ac.at.